

A SIMPLE MODELING APPROACH TO PREDICTING DAMAGE PROGRESS IN UNIDIRECTIONALLY ARRAYED CHOPPED STRAND LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Formability, as well as strength and stiffness, is important to utilize carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRPs) in automobiles for weight saving, because their components have complex geometries. However, the microstructure of composites with discontinuous fibers cannot be controlled when using conventional molding compounds, and therefore, enhancing all the properties is difficult. The unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS), in which a prepreg sheet with unidirectional and continuous reinforcing fibers is cut in a regular manner, are promising to overcome the difficulty. Although a UACS layer is an assembly of many small sheets, the high structural regularity leads to high mechanical properties. Analytical evaluation of UACS laminates is essential to optimize fiber-cutting (slit) pattern and to achieve better performance, but building a complex mesh near the slits is a severe obstacle. This study therefore proposes a simple approach to model the microstructure of UACS laminates and to predict their damage extension. UACS laminates have two key microstructures, namely the stacked layers and the slit pattern, and the layer-wise modeling and the extended finite-element method (XFEM) are adopted for the laminated structure and the discontinuities owing to slits, respectively. Static tensile strength of quasi-isotropic UACS laminates with diagonal continuous slits was predicted and compared with the reported experiment results. The predicted strength agreed well with the experiments, and the tensile strength of the UACS laminates increased with decreasing the inclined slit angle, owing to the less probability of delamination extension from the slits.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are promising for reducing structural weight and for improving fuel consumption efficiency of automobiles. Their components have complex geometries, and therefore, formability is important in addition to strength and stiffness. However, in general, enhancing all the properties is difficult, because the microstructure of composites with discontinuous fibers cannot be controlled when using conventional molding compounds. To overcome the difficulty, Taketa et al. [1] proposed unidirectionally arrayed chopped strands (UACS), in which a prepreg sheet with continuous and unidirectional reinforcing fibers is cut in a regular manner. A UACS layer is then an assembly of many small sheets, but the high structural regularity is the key difference from the sheet molding compounds (SMCs).

Experimental studies [1-3] demonstrated high mechanical properties and good formability of UACS laminates. In the case of the UACS laminates with diagonal continuous slits, both static strengths [2] and fatigue properties [4] were improved via a low slit angle. However, the mechanism of strength enhancement is unclear. Analytical evaluation of UACS laminates is thus essential to optimize fiber-cutting (slit) pattern and to achieve better performance. Li et al. [5] analyzed tensile damage of a UACS laminate having discontinuous angled slits by using a standard finite-element model that explicitly expressed the slit structure. The homogenization method was adopted to predict the effective elastic

constants of the middle UACS plies with decreased computation cost. Although discontinuity of fibers can be expressed by double nodes, modification of the slit layout requires rebuilding a complex mesh. This is a severe obstacle for optimization of the slit layout.

Therefore, this study presents a simple approach to model the microstructure of UACS laminates and to predict their damage extension. Static tensile strength of quasi-isotropic UACS laminates with diagonal continuous slits is predicted and compared with the experiment results [2] to verify the proposed approach. The effect of the angle between the slit and the fiber direction (hereafter referred to as the slit angle) is investigated analytically.

2 MODELING APPROACH FOR UACS LAMINATES

UACS laminates have two key microstructures, namely the stacked layers and the slit layout in a ply. A laminate is separated into some finite-element layers that correspond to the plies, and two-dimensional solid elements or plate elements are used for these layers. This layer-wise modeling [6] enables us to analyze deformation of each ply and to reduce calculation cost compared with a three-dimensional fine model. Adhesion and delamination of the finite-element layers are analyzed by cohesive elements inserted into layer interfaces. The following relationship between the traction T and relative displacement Δ is used [7]:

$$T_i = \frac{s}{1-s} \frac{\Delta_i}{\Delta_{ic}} \tau_{i,max} \quad (i = n, t, b) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta_{nc} = \frac{2G_{Ic}}{\tau_{n,max} s_{ini}}, \quad \Delta_{tc} = \frac{2G_{IIc}}{\tau_{t,max} s_{ini}}, \quad \Delta_{bc} = \frac{2G_{IIIc}}{\tau_{b,max} s_{ini}} \quad (2)$$

where τ_{max} is the maximum stress, Δ_c is the critical relative displacement at which the cohesive element becomes a crack, the subscript i denotes the cracking mode; n , t and b correspond to the mode I, II and III, respectively. G_{ic} ($i = I, II, III$) is the interlaminar fracture toughness. The parameter s represents the residual strength of the element, and its initial value s_{ini} is a value near unity. The parameter s is a function of the relative displacements normalized by its critical values:

$$s = \min \left(s_{min}, \max(0, 1 - |\tilde{\Delta}|) \right) \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{\Delta}$ is the normalized relative displacement vector. The above cohesive element acts as a penalty element that keeps continuity of the displacement field at the double nodes when the parameter s is the initial value. After the maximum stress is reached, the parameter s decreases with an increase of the relative displacement, and the element dissipates the elastic energy. Finally, the cohesive element becomes a crack when $s = 0$.

The extended finite-element method (XFEM) [8] is adopted to analyze discontinuity of the displacement field near the slits (i.e., fiber cutting lines). The XFEM can represent a crack independently of the finite-element mesh by enriching the interpolation function of the standard FEM with special functions. This characteristic enables us to use a regularly shaped mesh regardless of the slit layout and to significantly reduce effort of the cumbersome preprocess for slits compared with the standard approach using double nodes along the slits [6].

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 Analytical model

Figure 1 depicts schematic of the layer-wise finite-element model. The stacking sequence in the experimental work [2] was $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$, and four layers of 45° , 0° , -45° and 90° were prepared and adhered by cohesive elements. In addition to the three layer interfaces of $45^\circ/0^\circ$, $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ and $-45^\circ/90^\circ$, the top 90° layer and the bottom 45° layer were also coupled by cohesive elements to reproduce a periodic structure in the through-thickness direction and to reduce the effect of free surfaces on damage extension. Dimensions of the model were the same as the reported experiment [2]; the model was 150 mm long and 25 mm wide, and the thickness of a layer was 0.14 mm.

The analytical solution of the tensile strength of a UACS laminate considering delamination in pure-shear mode agreed well with the measured strength [1]. Therefore, this study assumed that the interlaminar shear deformation is dominant for delamination growth and that the crack opening mode due to the deformation in the through-thickness direction is negligible. Two-dimensional plane-stress elements were then adopted in the finite-element layers, and there were 61404 nodes and 60000 solid elements. The shape function includes an enrichment function near the slits owing to the use of the XFEM and is not a simple polynomial expression. Therefore, this study prepared nine integral points in each element for numerical integration.

Models with five slit angles (16° , 27° , 45° , 60° and 90°) were developed, and the effect of the slit angle θ on the damage extension and tensile strength was investigated. Figure 2 presents the sets of J-type nodes adjacent to the slits for $\theta=27^\circ$. The fiber length, i.e., the spacing between two adjacent slits, was 25 mm. The left edge of the model was fixed in the longitudinal direction, and uniform tensile displacement was applied to the right edge. Material properties used in the analysis are listed in Table 1. In order to compare the predictions with the experiment results [2], those of general-purpose CFRPs (T700S/#2500, Toray Industries) were adopted. In the experimental work [2], a cure cycle different from the standard one was applied, and therefore, the interlaminar fracture toughness estimated for this material [1] was used.

Although actual slits consist of polymer matrix flowed into the narrow gap along the fiber cutting lines, they break by small deformation. Slits are then assumed as straight cracks in this model. In this approach, damage growth and final failure of the whole laminate are analyzed by cohesive elements at the layer interfaces. It should be noted that the slits modeled by the XFEM (i.e., initially opening cracks) are the source of delamination onset and that crack growth is not predicted by the XFEM.

Figure 1: Schematic of the layer-wise finite-element model.

Figure 2: Finite-element mesh and distribution of J-type nodes (black) for the slit angle $\theta = 27^\circ$.

Table 1: Material properties used in the analysis.

(a) Mechanical properties of unidirectional CFRP

Longitudinal Young's modulus (GPa)	130
Transverse Young's modulus (GPa)	7.4
In-plane shear modulus (GPa)	4.5
In-plane Poisson's ratio	0.34

(b) Interlaminar properties

Mode II critical energy release rate (J/m^2)	633
Mode III critical energy release rate (J/m^2)	633
In-plane shear strength (MPa)	60
Out-of-plane shear strength (MPa)	60

3.2 Analytical results and discussion

Figure 3 depicts the predicted stress-strain curves. The stress linearly increased until 0.4% applied strain regardless of the slit angle. Young's modulus was 49.3–49.4 GPa, which was almost identical with the modulus calculated by the classical lamination theory without considering the slits (49.5 GPa). This accordance indicated that the slit spacing was sufficiently large for stress recovery. The modulus decreased after 0.4% applied strain, suggesting accumulation of damage in the cohesive elements. The maximum stress depended on the slit angle, because the applied strain at the rapid stress drop caused by delamination growth changed with the slit layout. Figure 4 presents the relationship between the predicted maximum stress and the slit angle θ along with the experiment results [2]. The maximum stress increased with decreasing θ within the range $\theta \leq 45^\circ$, and it was almost constant at other slit angles. The predictions agreed with the experiment, and this result demonstrated the validity of the proposed approach.

Figure 3: Predicted stress-strain curves of the UACS quasi-isotropic laminates.

Figure 4: Change in the maximum tensile stress by the slit angle.

Figure 5: Distribution of the parameter s of cohesive elements indicating delamination growth in a UACS quasi-isotropic laminate with the slit angle of 16° .

Figure 5 depicts process of delamination growth in the case of $\theta = 16^\circ$. As the applied strain increased, softening of the cohesive elements (i.e., decrease of the parameter s) proceeded along the slits of the 0° layer at the interfaces adjacent to the 0° layer. In particular, delamination grew from the intersection of the slits in the upper and lower layers near the edge of the model. However, even when the laminate was further loaded, the delamination accumulated only in a small area, and finally, delamination propagated rapidly and the applied stress decreased. This trend of delamination growth was observed in all the slit angles.

In all the slit angles, delamination accumulated significantly at the $45^\circ/0^\circ$ and $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ interfaces, and the other layer interfaces were almost intact until failure. Figure 6 then presents delamination of the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface before and after the reduction of the applied stress. The cohesive elements softened along the slit of 0° layer in all the slit angles. The 0° layer carries much higher tensile stress than the other layers, and the slits in the 0° layer are easy to open in both the modes I and II. Delamination along the slits in the 0° layer extends owing to the large displacement relative to the adjacent layer generated by opened slits. At small slit angles of 16° (Fig. 6a) and 27° (Fig. 6b), almost no delamination occurred until the maximum stress was reached, except for local areas near the edge in the transverse direction. In the case of small slit angles, the area surrounded by the slits in the upper and lower layers is small, and the delamination develops unstably in the area. In contrast, there is no area surrounded by the slits at large slit angles (Figs. 6c-6e). Delamination is generated from the edge and gradually extends along the slit of 0° layer prior to reaching the maximum stress with an increase of the applied strain. This observation indicates that the mechanism of delamination growth affected the maximum tensile stress of the UACS laminates.

Figure 6: Delamination of the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface before and after the step drop in the applied stress.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

A UACS layer is an assembly of many small sheets maintaining high structural regularity. The laminates using UACS achieved high strength and good formability simultaneously [1]. This study

presented a simple modeling approach for UACS laminates. The lamination structure and adhesion of the plies are modeled by developing finite-element layers for each ply and by inserting cohesive elements into the layer interfaces. Furthermore, the slits (i.e., fiber cutting lines) in the layers were represented using the XFEM. The XFEM enables us to introduce slits to the model independently of the mesh. This approach does not require to develop a complex mesh along the slits, and this characteristic significantly reduces the effort of the preprocess compared to the conventional double-node approach. In this model, delamination growth, as well as the failure of the laminate, is predicted by the cohesive elements at the layer interfaces, and the slits represented by the XFEM are the source of delamination onset.

Damage extension and tensile strength of quasi-isotropic UACS laminates with continuous diagonal slits were analyzed by the present approach and compared with the experiment results [2]. The predicted strength increased with a decrease in the slit angle, and the predicted change in the tensile strength to the slit angle agreed with the experiment. This consistency confirmed the present approach. In the case of small slit angles less than 11° , final failure of the laminate was caused by fiber breaks [2], and further improvement is necessary to investigate the whole relationship between the strength and slit angle.

In all the slit angles greater than 16° , delamination extended at the layer interfaces adjacent to the 0° layer, and the interfaces of $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ and $90^\circ/45^\circ$ were almost intact until final failure. In particular, delamination was hardly generated until reaching the maximum stress at a small slit angle and developed unstably in the area surrounded by the slits of the upper and lower layers at a certain applied strain, which caused a steep drop of the applied stress. In contrast, delamination extended gradually at slit angles greater than 45° . The strength of UACS laminates was influenced by such difference in the delamination growth owing to the slit angle.

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